

COAGULATION OF SOLS : VARIATION OF TIME OF COAGULATION WITH ELECTROLYTE CONCENTRATION. FURTHER STUDIES WITH As_2S_3 SOL

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Further data on the coagulation of As_2S_3 sol at different concentrations by electrolytes, e. g., $MgCl_2$, $CaCl_2$, $Sr(NO_3)_2$, $ZnSO_4$, $CdCl_2$, $MnCl_2$, $CrCl_3$, $UO_2(NO_3)_2$, $Ce(SO_4)_2$ and $Th(SO_4)_2$ have been presented. Interesting observations on the nature of the curves obtained have been made and explained in the light of the empirical equation of more general character, $c = a + b/t$ than the one deduced in an earlier communication by the authors.

In continuation of our previous publication (1951, 28, 179) on slow coagulation of colloids and the relation between the electrolyte concentration and the time of required coagulation, studied from the view point of the applicability of our empirical equation,

$$c = a + b \cdot 1/t,$$

we communicate further data on the coagulation of arsenious sulphide sol at different concentrations, by various other electrolytes. We have been able to elicit some more interesting observations on the nature of the curves obtained by plotting c against $1/t$, in the case of some electrolytes other than those previously communicated. We have attempted to explain such observations or anomalies by representing the process of slow coagulation by an empirical equation of more general character, of which $c = a + b/t$ is a particular case ; the normal and abnormal behaviours of the sol on dilution have also been studied.

EXPERIMENTAL

Arsenious sulphide sol was prepared by adding an arsenious oxide solution, from a burette dropwise, to water through which hydrogen sulphide was continuously bubbled, till a sol of desired opacity was produced. Excess of hydrogen sulphide was expelled by bubbling hydrogen through it for about 24 hours. In order to determine the time of coagulation by a definite volume of electrolyte solution of known concentration, five test tubes were taken. To each, the specified volume of electrolyte was added and then made up to 5 c.c. by adding the requisite amount of water. Five c. c. of the sol were taken in five other test tubes. The sol and the electrolyte were then thoroughly mixed and allowed to stand. The time at which the coagulated sol just began to leave the surface of the liquid, was noted and the mean of all the five values was taken as the time of coagulation. The following tables give the time of coagulation (in mins.) and its reciprocal corresponding to different amounts of various electrolytes ; is expressed in terms of millimoles added to 1 litre of the sol.

TABLE I
Coagulation with MgCl₂.
 Conc. of sol = 1.35g. of As₂S₃/litre (A).

Sol A			Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
c*	t.	1/t.	c*	t.	1/t.	c*	t.	1/t.
1.226	40 min.	0.0250	0.981	74 min.	0.0133	0.981	90 min.	0.0111
1.472	30	.0330	1.104	44	.0273	1.104	52	.0192
1.717	26	.0385	1.226	29	.0345	1.226	32	.03125
1.839	22	.0454	1.349	23	.0435	1.349	21	.0476
2.024	155	.0645	1.472	16	.0625	1.472	15	.0667
1.368	inf.	0	1.715	9	.1111	1.595	11	.0909
			1.497	inf.	0	1.552	inf.	0

TABLE II
Coagulation with CaCl₂.
 Conc. of sol = 1.35g. of As₂S₃/litre (A).

Sol A			Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.9091	61 min.	0.0164	0.909	51 min.	0.0196	0.788	40 min.	0.0111
1.0912	43	.0232	1.091	33	.0333	0.9093	41	.0244
1.212	36	.0278	1.212	17	.0588	1.091	20	.0500
1.455	31	.0322	1.455	11	.0509	1.212	12	.0833
1.697	24	.0417	1.697	7	.1428	1.455	7	.1428
1.340	11	.0909	1.485	inf.	0	1.642	inf.	0.
1.424	inf.	0						

TABLE III
Coagulation with Sr(NO₃)₂.
 Conc. of sol = 0.908g. As₂S₃/litre (A).

Sol A			Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.492	61 min.	0.0164	0.492	105 min.	0.0095	0.591	42 min.	0.0238
.591	36	.0277	.542	64	.0156	.640	30	.0333
.689	27	.0370	.591	38	.0263	.689	22	.0454
.837	20	.0500	.689	24	.0416	.788	14	.0714
.985	15	.0667	.788	17	.0588	.886	10	.1000
1.083	12.5	.0800	.985	12	.0833	1.492	inf.	0
1.345	inf.	0	1.394	inf.	0			

TABLE IV

*Coagulation with ZnSO₄.*Conc. of sol = 0.9080g. As₂S₃/litre (A).

Sol A			Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
1.528	48 min.	0.0208	0.1146	95 min.	0.0105	0.1337	50 min.	0.0200
1.719	34	.0294	.1337	55	.0182	.1528	36	.0277
1.910	20	.6500	.1528	37	.0270	.1719	20	.0500
2.101	10	.1000	.1719	22	.0454	.1910	10	.1000
1.05	inf.	0	.1910	13	.0769	.859	inf.	0
			.2101	8	.125			
			.955	inf.	0			

TABLE V

*Coagulation with CdCl₂.*Conc. of sol = 0.7573g. As₂S₃/litre (A).

Sol A			Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
1.158	80 min.	0.0125	1.158	62 min.	0.1580	1.042	50 min.	0.0200
1.273	45	.0222	1.273	40	.0250	1.158	41	.0244
1.389	35	.0286	1.505	27	.0370	1.273	32	.03150
1.505	29	.0345	1.736	18	.0566	1.389	25	.04000
1.736	19	.0526	1.968	8.5	.1176	1.621	17	.0588
1.968	11	.0309	1.344	inf.	0	1.852	11	.0909
1.984	inf.	0				1.810	inf.	0

TABLE VI

*Coagulation with MnCl₂.*Conc. of sol = 0.7573g. As₂S₃/litre (A).

Sol A			Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.374	58 min.	0.0172	0.876	101 min.	0.0099	0.876	120 min.	0.0083
1.071	44	.0227	0.974	60	.0167	0.974	72	.0139
1.168	23	.0435	1.071	42	.0238	1.071	46	.0217
1.266	18	.0567	1.168	30	.0333	1.168	32	.03125
1.460	10	.1000	1.266	22	.0454	1.266	22	.0454
1.655	7	.1428	1.363	15	.0667	1.363	17	.0588
1.487	inf.	0	1.535	inf.	0	1.633	inf.	0

TABLE VII

Coagulation with CrCl₃.
 Conc. of sol = 0.9080g. As₂S₃/litre (A).

c.	Sol A		Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.0837	78 min.	0.0128	0.0851	54 min.	0.0185	0.6962	43 min.	0.0232
0.1026	43	0.0222	0.1026	26	0.0385	0.1122	18	0.0556
0.1154	28	0.0357	0.1115	21	0.0476	0.1168	7	0.1428
0.1282	20.5	0.0488	0.1295	14	0.0714	0.1282	4	0.2500
0.1548	9.0	0.1111						

TABLE VIII

Coagulation with UO₂(NO₃)₂.
 Conc. of sol = 0.9080g. As₂S₃/litre (A).

c.	t.	Sol A		Sol 3A/4	
		1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.964	36 min.	0.0277	1.205	66 min.	0.0151
1.084	29	0.0345	1.265	53	0.0193
1.205	24	0.0417	1.326	38	0.0263
1.326	21	0.0476	1.386	25	0.0400
1.446	14	0.0714	1.507	17	0.0588
1.681	6	0.1667			

TABLE IX

Coagulation with Ce(SO₄)₂.
 Conc. of sol = 0.9080g. of As₂S₃ / litre (A).

c.	Sol A		Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.2513	54 min.	0.0185	0.1728	82 min.	0.0122	0.1728	90 min.	0.0104
0.2828	31	0.0323	0.1855	60	0.0167	0.2042	45	0.0222
0.3142	17	0.0588	0.2199	33	0.0333	0.2357	28	0.0357
0.3770	6	0.1667	0.2357	26	0.0385	0.2671	16	0.0625
0.4084	5	0.2000	0.2513	19	0.0526			
0.1728	inf.	0	0.2828	6	0.1667			
			0.1070	inf.	0			

TABLE X

Coagulation with Th(SO₄)₂.
 Conc. of sol = 0.7573g. As₂S₃/litre (A).

Sol A	t.	1/t.	Sol 3A/4			Sol A/2		
			c.	t.	1/t.	c.	t.	1/t.
0.2698	56 min.	0.0178	0.2023	44 min.	0.0227	0.1686	48 min.	0.025
0.3035	40	0.0250	0.2698	25	0.0400	0.2023	28	0.0357
0.3372	39	0.0256	0.3372	16	0.0625	0.2698	20	0.0500
0.3710	34	0.0294	0.4046	12	0.0833	0.3372	16	0.0625
0.4046	28	0.0357	0.4721	10	0.1000	0.4046	11.5	0.0909
0.4721	24	0.0417				0.4958	9	0.1111
0.5901	20	0.0500						
1.1012	inf.	0						

DISCUSSION

From the c and $1/t$ curves (only the curve relating to CaCl_2 shown) it will be observed that these are of a continuous straight line nature, at all dilutions of the sol, when the precipitating electrolytes are $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_4)_2$, while there are bends towards $1/t$ axis at higher values of ' c ' in the case of MgCl_2 , CaCl_2 , ZnSO_4 , CdCl_2 , CrCl_3 , $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2$, MnCl_2 and $\text{Ce}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ as coagulating electrolytes.

FIG. 1
Coagulation with CaCl_2 .

An interesting feature of these bends is that in most cases the two parts of the curves can be represented by two straight lines and the inclination between these two straight lines is almost the same for all dilutions of the sol. The following table, keeping in view the accuracy of this experiment, clearly illustrates this point.

TABLE XI

Inclination.

	Sol A.	Sol 3A/4.	Sol A/2.
ZnSO ₄	45°	42°	50°
CdCl ₂	23°	23°	20°
MnCl ₂	35°	34°	38°
MgCl ₂	40°	38°	42°
CrCl ₃	37°	...	37°
CaCl ₂	47°	40°	25°
Ce(SO ₄) ₂	44°	52°	...

The coagulation curves for Sr(NO₃)₂, CaCl₂ and MgCl₂ bring out another interesting point with regard to the effect of dilution of the sol. These curves, unlike others, intersect at some distance from the 'c' axis. For values of 'c' greater than those given by the points of intersection, the dilution effect is normal; but it becomes abnormal for values lower than the points of intersection. This connotes that the abnormal behaviour of a sol has its own limits, and, in some cases, the so-called normality may change into abnormality if the electrolyte concentration is kept below a certain value, which may be designated as the inversion concentration point of the electrolyte.

In considering the bend of the curves, two lines of approach are probable. One of them lies in considering the time of coagulation as a discontinuous function of the electrolyte concentration. If it is so, there are two parts of *c* and *1/t* curve, each being a straight line, as is shown in the graph above. This discontinuity suggests that, after a certain concentration of the electrolyte, the values of the constants 'a' and 'b' in the equation $c = a + b/t$ are altered. It is yet early to establish a theory to explain this sudden change in the values of 'a' and 'b'.

The other aspect of explaining the bend may be based on the assumption that the curve is a continuous one. If this assumption is acceptable, a more generalised expression can be suggested to represent the whole curve—an expression of which $c = a + b/t$ is a particular case. This expression, which is as good an empirical one as the expression $c = a + b/t$, is as follows.

$$c = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t}$$

where *a*, *m* and *n* are constants and 'c' and 't' have their usual significance.

The above equation represents a hyperbola the bend of which is dependent on the values of the constants *m* and *n*, and when 'n' is very large in comparison to *1/t*, the above equation reduces to $c = a + \frac{m}{n} \cdot 1/t$

or
$$c = a + b \cdot 1/t \left(\text{putting } \frac{m}{n} = b \right)$$

which is the equation previously communicated. In order to confirm the validity of the above expression $c = a + \frac{m \cdot 1/t}{n + 1/t}$ it is necessary to evaluate the values of the constants a , ' m ' and ' n ' and to see to what extent the hypothetical curve, obtained with the help of these values of the constants, agrees with the curve actually obtained. The constant ' a ' is given by the point of intersection on the concentration axis and ' m ' and ' n ' can be evaluated from the equations obtained by substituting two or three suitable chosen experimental value of c and $1/t$. The hypothetical curves thus obtained very nearly superimpose the experimental one in most cases. These hypothetical curves have been shown by dotted lines in the accompanying graph. Further work to elucidate this equation is in progress and will be communicated shortly.

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